

GLOBAL CHALLENGES TO DIALOGIC PRACTICES IN CLASSROOMS

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Abstract:

This article paves the way for future research that aim to examine the effects of authentic dialogue has on the social and emotional competences of children in general and preschoolers in particular. The research question of "Can authentic dialogue be achieved between teachers and children through teaching?" It can only be attempted to be answered if there is an understanding of the importance this type of dialogue has on children's development.

Key words: authentic, dialogic practices , characteristics, interpretation.

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Young children experience learning via their basic five senses and are not developmentally capable of understanding abstract terms rather only concrete ones Their teachers scaffold their learning, both socially and emotionally through dialogue, unfortunately, the pandemic prevents these interactions. In addition, the reports that parents are also under a great deal of pandemic related stress, such as health worries and employment issues and find it difficult to function because their anxiety levels are so high. Most often, they cannot seek help from their most natural support groups such as grandparents or other close family members due to the restrictions on gatherings and therefore, often find themselves socially isolated compromising their parental capabilities. Teachers can play a great role in assisting parents by conducting authentic personal dialogues with them in which they can listen to their own needs, express empathy and lower their fear levels, in turn this will prove beneficial for their children as well. In addition, teachers need to find a way to conduct authentic dialogue with children in order to support their emotional needs during this challenging period in world history. Can it be done through a computer screen? Can teachers provide an open dialogic space with the expectation that children will be able to speak their thoughts and their feelings when they are surrounded by other family members at home, in a noisy environment rather than having a face-to-face talk with their them. The child explores what the teacher's reactions are stressful situations and how they can help them understand what is going on around them. In normative times, preschool teachers testify to the fact that preschoolers feel more comfortable speaking of their fears with their teachers because they know that they won't be judged or reprimanded as they would be by a parent.

The challenge of creating more inclusive public schools addressing the needs of the 21st century Knowledge Society is a major one. Extensive work has been reported regarding the promotion of social inclusion policies in education mainly in two directions: a) Towards the inclusion of "objectively" excluded populations such as immigrants, low-income, and

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socially, mentally or physically disadvantaged students; b) Towards the inclusion of “subjectively” excluded populations in aspects such as media, digital or critical literacy skills. However, inclusion does not only regard specific groups of learners and their limited access to material or non-material resources, including knowledge and skills; recent efforts of public schools towards a more inclusive education tend to focus on the classroom climate and the fostering of “learning for all” opportunities, for example through whole-class dialogue. Dialogic teaching can be broadly defined as an approach for “teaching and learning through, for and as dialogue”.

Although there are different approaches to dialogic teaching, authors agree on the following aspects: 1) Dialogic teaching must be intentional Learnt as per its adherence to principles and routine practices with a dialogic quality. Students’ agency, manifested in them acting “authoritatively and accountably (problematizing and solving issues)” is the other necessary side for dialogic teaching to emerge in a successful way. The role of teachers in allowing and fostering productive and constructive dialogue is essential in this regard. Several scholars have argued that dialogic teaching is difficult and gradual to develop. Such difficulty is even greater when it comes to teachers orchestrating whole-class discussions, and it is mainly related to the effective facilitation and mediation of students’ contributions with the aim of reinforcing their own participation and accountability. For instance, it has been observed that even when teachers become able to open genuine dialogical discussions with at least three students participating in those for at least 30 seconds, teachers’ and students’ capacity to refer back to the discussion contents in ways that incentivise genuine contribution of ideas by the same or different students remains limited. This capacity refers to the concept of ‘cumulativity’ of discourse introduced by Alexander, which forms one of the main principles of dialogic teaching, together with: ‘purposefulness’ (i.e. teachers planning and steering classroom talk with specific educational goals in mind), ‘collectiveness’ (i.e. teachers and children addressing learning tasks together), ‘reciprocity’ (i.e. teachers and children listening to each other, sharing ideas and considering alternatives), and ‘supportiveness’ (i.e. students expressing their ideas freely without the fear of wrong answers and helping each other to reach common understandings). The present study is part of a multi-country, cross-sectional (pre-primary, primary and secondary) largescale intervention project focusing on the acquisition of dialogic teaching practices and implementation with the goal of fostering cultural literacy learning skills among students. As part of this project, cultural literacy was defined as a dynamic set of dispositions, resulting from social, dialogical practice which leads the individuals to an empathetic, tolerant and inclusive acceptance of “the other”. This study fcuses on inclusion as a teacher’s disposition towards students, as manifested in inclusive dialogic teaching talk moves resulting in more or less dialogic student moves in Portuguese and Spanish secondary classrooms.

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